

УДК 616.831-001.31

DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7188203>

APPLICATION OF SENSORY DEPRIVATION IN INSOMNIA IN PATIENTS WITH LONG-TERM CONSEQUENCES OF MILD COMBAT TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURY

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ЗАСТОСУВАННЯ СЕНСОРНОЇ ДЕПРИВАЦІЇ ПРИ РОЗЛАДАХ СНУ У ХВОРИХ З ВІДДАЛЕНИМИ НАСЛІДКАМИ ЛЕГКОЇ БОЙОВОЇ ЧЕРЕПНО-МОЗКОВОЇ ТРАВМИ

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ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ СЕНСОРНОЙ ДЕПРИВАЦИИ ПРИ НАРУШЕНИЯХ СНА У БОЛЬНЫХ С ОТДАЛЕННЫМИ ПОСЛЕДСТВИЯМИ ЛЕГКОЙ БОЕВОЙ ЧЕРЕПНО-МОЗГОВОЙ ТРАВМЫ

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Summary/Резюме

Night sleep of 49 patients with long-term consequences of mild combat traumatic brain injury was carried out. All the patients under observation were hospitalized in the clinic of Institute of Neurology, Psychiatry and Addiction of the National Academy of

Medical Sciences of Ukraine. The patients with severe clinical symptoms had significant changes of sleep indicators. For example, the process of falling asleep was prolonged, the duration of delta sleep, the phase of slow-wave sleep, and the number of completed sleep cycles was reduced. In addition, the average heart rate during sleep increased significantly, which indicates an increase in sympatho-adrenal effects on the tension of the mechanisms of autonomic support. The complexity of the treatment of such patients forced to use the method of sensory deprivation to correct sleep disorders. The proposed method caused positive changes in sleep. Adherence to this method of three-day use of sleeping pills "Levan" significantly enhanced the positive effects of sensory deprivation due to more significant changes in humoral regulation.

Key words: *sensory deprivation, consequences of combat traumatic brain injury, sleep disorders, autonomic nervous system, melatonin.*

Изучен ночной сон 49 пациентов с отдаленными последствиями боевой черепно-мозговой травмы легкой степени. Все находившиеся под наблюдением пациенты были госпитализированы в клинику Института неврологии, психиатрии и наркологии НАМН Украины. У больных с выраженной клинической симптоматикой наблюдались значительные изменения показателей сна. К примеру, удлинялся процесс засыпания, уменьшалась длительность дельта-сна, фазы медленного сна, количество завершенных циклов сна. Кроме того, средняя частота сердечных сокращений во время сна значительно выросла, что свидетельствует об усилении симпатoadреналового воздействия на напряжение механизмов вегетативной поддержки. Сложность лечения у таких пациентов заставила использовать метод сенсорной депривации для коррекции нарушений сна. Предлагаемый способ вызвал положительные изменения сна. При соблюдении такой методики трехдневного снотворного приема «Леван» значительно усиливались положительные эффекты сенсорной депривации за счет более существенных изменений гуморальной регуляции.

Ключевые слова: *сенсорная депривация, боевой черепно-мозговой травмы, расстройства сна, вегетативная нервная система, мелатонин.*

Проведено дослідження нічного сну 49 пацієнтів з віддаленими наслідками бойової черепно-мозгової травми легкого ступеня. Усі пацієнти, які перебували під спостереженням, були госпіталізовані в клініку Інституту неврології, психіатрії та наркології НАМН України. У хворих з вираженою клінічною симптоматикою спостерігалися значні зміни показників сну. Наприклад, подовжувався процес засинання, зменшувалася тривалість дельта-сну, фази повільного сну, кількість завершених циклів сну. Крім того, середня частота серцевих скорочень під час сну значно зросла, що свідчить про посилення симпато-адреналового впливу на напругу механізмів вегетативної підтримки. Складність лікування таких пацієнтів змусила використовувати метод сенсорної депривації для корекції порушень сну. Запропонований спосіб викликав позитивні зміни сну. При дотриманні такої методики триденного прийому снодійного «Леван» значно посилювались позитивні ефекти сенсорної депривації за рахунок більш істотних змін гуморальної регуляції.

Ключові слова: *сенсорна депривація, наслідки бойової черепно-мозгової травми, розлади сну, вегетативна нервова система, мелатонін.*

Introduction

Military actions in eastern Ukraine lead to an increase in the number of patients with the consequences of mine-explosive injury which has pathogenesis of its own, and its clinical and morphological, neurophysiological manifestations are much more difficult [1, 2, 3]. Brain damage in combat traumatic brain injury (CTBI) is associated primarily with the direct action of the blast wave, sharp fluctuations in atmospheric pressure, exposure to sound waves, the effect of sharp acceleration of the victim, excessive irritation of extra- and interreceptors on a large body surface which causes excessive afferent impulses and the formation of numerous and persistent foci of excitation in the central nervous system (CNS). This contributes to persistent violations of the mechanisms of regulation of metabolic processes [1, 4, 5]. Accordingly, the consequences of CTBI are more severe and long-lasting than domestic traumatic brain injury [6, 7].

All further dynamics of post-traumatic changes in the long term can be represented either as a process of compensation and completion of recovery of regulatory systems, or as a process of incomplete compensation, which ultimately leads to persistent violations of regulatory mechanisms of functional systems [8]. Lack of compensatory reactions, in turn, leads to the formation of progressive clinical disorders, most often in the autonomic nervous system (ANS), which significantly impairs the adaptive responses of patients. In addition, 100 % of patients in this group have sleep disorders, which leads to a deterioration in their quality of life.

The effects of changes in the ANS are realized through a system of humoral regulation, which is based on catecholamines (adrenaline, norepinephrine), which is part of the set of hormones and mediators of the sympathoadrenal system. They allow a rapid, adequate transition of

the body from a state of rest to a state of excitement, regulating and directing the course of homeostatic processes.

The regulation of sleep processes is subordinated to one of this system hormones — melatonin, which is a neuropeptide and produced by the pineal gland.

The treatment of such patients is quite a difficult task, so for the first time we decided to use the method of sensory deprivation in sleep disorders.

Materials and methods

We examined 49 patients aged 29 — 40 y. o. who in 2014 — 2017 were in the combat zone and received a minor mine — explosive injury. In the acute period the injury they all were treated in the neurological department of a military hospital. The criteria for including patients in the study were: participation in hostilities in eastern Ukraine; term after the last mine-explosive injury 13 months and more; absence of focal lesions of the brain according to nuclear magnetic resonance imaging (NMRI); absence of somatic, autoimmune and endocrine diseases; lack of alcohol and drug addiction.

All the subjects gave informed consent to participate in the examination and processing of their personal data (Order of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine dated January 21, 2016 N 29), as well as in compliance with moral and ethical principles in accordance with the main provisions of the World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki (1994, 2000, 2008) and the positive decision of the Commission on Bioethics of the Institute for Neurology, Psychiatry and Addiction of the National Academy of Medical Sciences of Ukraine” (Kharkov, Ukraine).

Upon admission to the institute’s clinic, all patients underwent a detailed clinical-neurological, autonomic examination, X-ray of the cervical spine, neurophysiological studies — electroencephalography (EEG), echoencephalography

(Echo-EG), ultrasound examination of the brains vessels and polygraphic registration of night sleep.

Studies of ANS indicators were performed according to the generally accepted method [9]. The study of the neuro-hormonal part of the sympathoadrenal system (adrenaline, noradrenaline) was performed using an analyzer and test system chromatograph (HPLC (Agilent) with ECD, Agilent Technologies, USA) and melatonin (Gammamaster, Pharmacia LKB Biotechnology AB, Sweden; LDN Labor Diagnostica Nord GmbH, Germany) — blood samples were taken at 4 o'clock in the morning under red light.

Sensory deprivation (SD) was performed every other day in a special chamber completely isolated from light, heat, sound and gravitational stimuli; the camera was 3 meters long and 2 meters wide [10]. The temperature inside the chamber was constantly maintained at 34° C. The depth of the bath is 25-27 cm and it is filled with liquid saturated Epson salt, which allows the patient to be on the surface, in a state close to weightlessness. Legs, arms, head, torso are supported by water thickness independently of each other, which mimics weightlessness. After each session the water is purified. It includes three stages of mechanical filtration and one stage of adsorption (water passes through activated carbon) and 8 stages of purification with the use of ultraviolet filters. The course of treatment is 7-12 sessions. The duration of the session is 40 — 60 minutes.

To assess the state of brain's bio-electrical activity, all patients underwent EEG recording in the dynamics. EEG recording was performed using a computer system "NEURON-SPECTRUM +" using 20 standard monopolar leads on the system "10-20" with two ipsilateral ear electrodes: Fp1A1, Fp2A2, F3A1, F4A2, FzA1, C3A1 P3A1, P4A2, PzA1, F7A1, F8A2, T3A1, T4A2, T5A1, T6A2, O1A1, O2A2, OzA2.

Objective study of night sleep — polysomnography (PSG) was performed using a computer system "NEURON-SPECTRUM +" with parallel registration of electroencephalogram (EEG), electrooculogram (EOG), electromyogram (EMG) and electrocardiogram (ECG).

The EEG included four monopolar channels, namely the central lead (C3 and C4) and the occipital lead (O1 and O2) for the left and right hemispheres of the brain in accordance with the international system "10-20". EEG leads were recorded relative to the left (A1) and right (A2) mastoid electrodes. EOG included two channels for recording potentials from the electrodes, one of which was located 1 cm above the outer corner of the left eye, and the other — 1 cm below the outer corner of the right eye. The mastoid electrode A1 was used as a reference electrode. EMG recording was performed using an additional polygraphic channel from the electrodes located in the chin area — one at the top of the chin and the other slightly lower, the distance between the electrodes was 2 — 3 cm. To record the ECG signal a lead from one electrode located in the lower part of the chest along the mid-clavicular line was used. Assessment of stages and phases of night sleep was carried out according to the International Classification of Stages and Phases of Sleep. In the analysis of the structure of night sleep, the analysis of the stages of sleep and the construction of hypnograms the epoch of analysis lasting 30 seconds was used. The calculation of night sleep was performed using the software "NEURON-SPECTRUM-PSG". Joint changes in the parameters of these indicators allow to objectively characterize the state of wakefulness and identify the phases and stages of night sleep [1]. After a preliminary detailed examination with the aim to improve sleep patients were given Levana IC at a dose of 0.5 mg 30-60 minutes before bedtime for the first three

days of their stay in the clinic. Levana IC is a benzodiazepine derivative, a selective agonist of the GABRA receptor apparatus, it shortens sleep and prolongs the slow-wave stage of sleep. It has a pronounced hypnotic, anxiolytic effect, moderate muscle relaxant and anticonvulsant effect. The peculiarity of the hypnotic effect of the drug is its ability to increase the duration of not only slow-wave but also paradoxical sleep with a constant number of episodes, which makes the hypnotic effect of the drug more physiological.

Statistical data processing was performed using the non-parametric Mann-Whitney test.

Results and discussion

41 (84 %) patients admitted to the clinic complained about headache, autonomic disorders and sleep-wake disorders. Their sleep disturbances were clinically characterized by a superficial nature of sleep, lack of rest, severe drowsiness during the day, morning headache, premature awakening, weakness and brokenness during the day. All this is due to dysfunction and imbalance between activating and synchronizing processes in non-specific brain structures that are responsible for the sleep-wake cycle.

The sympathoadrenal system in the subjects, namely its neurotransmitter link indicators (adrenaline, noradrenaline) were sharply reduced at their hospitalization and dopamine content increased (Table 1). After a course of sensory deprivation catecholamines indicators returned to normal and adrenaline content was close to control.

Deterioration of sleep in most subjects coincided with low lev-

els of melatonin in the blood. This figure was within the physiological corridor only in 6 (12 %) patients. After treatment, the number of people with normal melatonin levels increased from 6 to 24 (24 %) ($p < 0.05$), which indicates a positive effect of this method on the excretion of melatonin in patients with consequences of trauma.

Studies of cerebral electrogenesis changes in patients with long-term effects of combat traumatic brain injury (CTBI) showed that 32.0 % of them had a dominated low-amplitude polymorphic activity on EEG; in fronto-temporal leads single acute waves were fixed. After functional loads synchronization processes were intensified on the EEG, this was manifested by the amplitude and index of alpha oscillations increases, representation of low-frequency activity and sharp waves increased, too.

The dominance of synchronized high-amplitude alpha activity, diffuse flashes of paroxysmal alpha activity modulated by sharp waves was determined in 12.0 % of patients' EEG. On 40.0 % of EEG's regular alpha activity with preserved occipital-frontal gradient was registered, low-amplitude single sharp waves were observed in the fronto-temporal leads, functional loads led to increased amplitude of alpha activity and diffuse activity in alpha range. In 16.0 % of patients on the EEG there was

Table 1

Dynamics of catecholamines before and after sensory deprivation in patients with the consequences of mild combat traumatic brain injury

Catecholamines	Before treatment	After treatment
Adrenaline (up to 50 ng/l)	19	44 *
Norepinephrine (110.0 — 410.0 ng/l)	71.3	134.8 *
Dopamine (up to 87 ng/l)	102	74 *

Note: * — significant changes are calculated between indicators before and after treatment

Table 2

Dynamics of melatonin before and after sensory deprivation in patients with the consequences of combat traumatic brain injury

Melatonin level	Before treatment		After treatment	
	Absolute numbers	%	Absolute numbers	%
High > 20 pg/ml	5	10	9	18
Norm 10-20 pg/ml	6	12	24	49
Low < 10 pg/ml	38	78	16	33

Table 3

Indicators of normalized spectral power of brain biopotentials according to background EEG data in patients in the dynamics of treatment (%)

Leads of EEG	Background EEG indicators	
	Before treatment	After treatment
Indicators of normalized spectral power biopotentials of the beta of LF range		
P3A1	9.01 ± 1.46	6.01 ± 1.50 *
P4A2	6.67 ± 0.86	5.08 ± 1.04 *
PzA1	8.53 ± 1.58	6.03 ± 1.47 *
T5A1	8.38 ± 1.35	4.98 ± 1.94 *
T6A2	5.87 ± 0.64	4.39 ± 0.75 *

Note: * — significant changes are calculated between indicators before and after treatment

a disorganization of bioelectrical activity of the brain, smoothing of regional differences with the formation at the background of functional loads diffuse flashes of polymorphic paroxysmal activity.

Thus, the visual analysis of EEG showed that the patients under examination had signs of brain's bioelectrical activity changes, and this indicated varying degrees of severity of dysfunction of non-specific brain systems of diencephalic-stem level.

According to the visual analysis of the brain bioelectrical activity of the patients under examination its positive dy-

namics was determined after the course of treatment. This was manifested by decrease of cerebral and paroxysmal changes severity on the EEG.

According to the results of spectral

analysis of EEG before and after the treatment, significant changes in the indicators of normalized spectral power of brain biopotentials were determined (Table 3). After a course of sensory deprivation, a significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease in the normalized spectral power of the biopotentials of the beta LF range in the parietal (P3A1, P4A2, PzA1) and posterior temporal (T5A1, T6A2) leads of both hemispheres was found. These data correlated with positive changes in clinical indicators, namely with a decrease in the intensity of headache and its frequency, improvement of psycho-emotional state,

manifested by a decrease in anxiety and irritability, improved sleep at night.

Coherent analysis of background EEG was also performed. Data on the dynamics of interhemispheric coherence of brain biopotentials in the dynamics of treatment are given in Table 4.

It was proved that after treatment hemispheric connections in the alpha rhythm range in the central (C3C4) leads significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased and inter-

Table 4

Indicators of interhemispheric coherence of brain biopotentials in the dynamics of treatment in absolute units

Leads of EEG	Indicators of EEG	
	Before treatment	After treatment
Indicators of interhemispheric coherence of biopotentials of alpha range		
C3C4	63.80 ± 7.77	75.80 ± 4.50
Indicators of interhemispheric coherence of beta potentials of the low-range range		
P3P4	65.20 ± 4.24	56.80 ± 4.32
Indicators of interhemispheric coherence of biopotentials of the beta HF range		
F7F8	56.80 ± 2.08	52.60 ± 1.99

Note: * — significant changes are calculated between indicators before and after treatment

Table 5

Indicators of intrahemispheric coherence of brain biopotentials in the dynamics of treatment (in absolute units)

EEG leads	EEG indicators	
	Before treatment	After treatment
Indicators of intrahemispheric coherence of beta biopotentials in LF range		
P3O1	81.8 ± 1.0	70.6 ± 3.7 *
F4C4	79.2 ± 4.7	85.6 ± 4.6 *
C4P4	80.2 ± 1.5	87.4 ± 1.2 *
P4O2	79.2 ± 3.4	72.4 ± 3.7 *
F8T4	81.6 ± 2.0	85.2 ± 1.4 *
T4T6	80.2 ± 1.3	78.2 ± 4.3 *
Indicators of intrahemispheric coherence of beta biopotentials in HF range		
P3O1	79.6 ± 0.8	74.0 ± 1.5
F8T4	75.0 ± 2.6	75.0 ± 2.6

Note: * — significant changes are calculated between pre- and post-treatment indicators

Indicators on the scale of night sleep quality and Epworth's daytime sleepiness questionnaire in dynamics (in points)

Indicators	Periods	
	Before treatment	After treatment
Scale of night sleep quality	16.0 ± 0.8	19.5 ± 0.6 *
Epworth's questionnaire	10.0 ± 0.4	7.5 ± 0.6 *

Note: * — significant changes are calculated between indicators before and after treatment

hemispheric connections in the beta LF range in the parietal (P3P4) leads weakened. In beta HF range in the lower temporal (F7F8) leads they weakened, too. These data correlated with the data of the dynamics of normalized spectral power and with the positive dynamics of clinical symptoms in the patients under treatment. Along with the indicators of interhemispheric coherence, the dynamics of indicators of intrahemispheric coherence of brain biopotentials during treatment was calculated and analyzed. Changes in intrahemispheric coherence of brain biopotentials in the dynamics of treatment are shown in Table 5.

As can be seen from Table 5 after treatment there was a significant increase in intrahemispheric coherence in beta LF range in frontal (F4C4), fronto-temporal

(F8T4) and central parietal (C4P4) leads with a predominance of the right hemisphere of the brain. Indicators of intrahemispheric coherence in beta LF range of the parieto-occipital (P3O1, P4O2) leads of both hemispheres of the brain and in the posterior temporal leads of the right hemisphere of the brain decreased. A significant increase in intrahemispheric coherence in the fronto-temporal (F8T4) leads of the right hemisphere and a decrease in intrahemispheric coherence in the parieto-occipital (P3O1) leads of the left hemisphere were also observed in the beta range of HF frequencies.

Thus, after treatment intrahemispheric ligaments in beta LF and beta HF rhythms, mainly in the frontal and central leads increased, while in the parieto-occipital and posterior temporal leads intrahemispheric ligaments in beta LF and beta HF rhythms have weakened. The latter indicates greater activation of the frontal

lobes of the brain, controlling and regulating voluntary mental activity. In addition, according to spectral and coherent analysis of background EEG after treatment an increase in intercentral and intrahemispheric interactions of biopotentials in beta LF and beta HF ranges in the fronto-central parts took place, but in the parieto-occipital departments of the brain there was a decrease in these indicators. This correlates with the positive dynamics

Average indicators on the questionnaire for assessing the quality of night sleep in the dynamics (in points)

Indicators	Period	
	Before treatment	After treatment
Anxiety, fear when going to sleep	10.0 ± 0.4	7.5 ± 0.6 *
Inability to sleep for more than 30 minutes	1.00 ± 0.08	0.50 ± 0.09*
Superficial sleep with many dreams	1.00 ± 0.01	1.25 ± 0.05*
Superficial sleep with night awakenings	2.00 ± 0.08	1.25 ± 0.05*
Night awakenings with complaints of headache	1.00 ± 0.01	0.75 ± 0.05*
Difficulty falling asleep after waking up	1.25 ± 0.03	0.75 ± 0.05*
Nightmares	0.25 ± 0.05	0.50 ± 0.09*
Sleepwalking	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00
Sleep talking	0.50 ± 0.09	0.25 ± 0.05*
Rhythmic movements during sleep	1.50 ± 0.09	1.25 ± 0.05*
Grinding teeth in sleep	0.75 ± 0.05	0.75 ± 0.05*
Night sweats	0.75 ± 0.05	0.50 ± 0.09*
Early final awakening	2.00 ± 0.08	1.50 ± 0.09*
Feelings that have not slept, fatigue when waking up after a night's sleep	2.50 ± 0.07	1.25 ± 0.05*
Lack of night sleep	1.00 ± 0.01	0.75 ± 0.05*
Daytime sleep	1.50 ± 0.09	1.25 ± 0.05*
Daytime sleepiness	1.75 ± 0.05	1.25 ± 0.05*

Note: * — significant changes ($p < 0.05$) were calculated between indicators before and after treatment

Table 8 after treatment re-

The average values of sleep at night in the dynamics

Indicators of night sleep	Period		P
	Before treatment	After treatment	
Latent period 1, min	12.7 ± 3.4	13.3 ± 7.7	0.66
Latent period 2, min	5.9 ± 1.4	15.2 ± 13.9	0.21
Latent period of delta-sleep	17.6 ± 3.1	9.7 ± 1.6	0.11
Latent period of REM sleep, min	75.1 ± 13.5	57.5 ± 6.9	0.24
length of sleepless period, min	48.4 ± 10.2	46.5 ± 11.8	0.83
Length 1, min	7.2 ± 1.4	1.7 ± 0.6	0.05
Length 2, min	230.9 ± 12.9	226.3 ± 27.8	0.83
Length of delta-sleep, min	95.6 ± 3.3	130.7 ± 18.9	0.03
Duration of REM, min	90.6 ± 10.0	89.5 ± 9.9	0.28
Duration of slow-wave sleep, min	333.7 ± 13.4	358.7 ± 3.7	0.15
Representation of wakefulness, %	9.3 ± 2.0	9.3 ± 2.2	0.96
Representation N1, %	1.6 ± 0.3	0.34 ± 0.0	0.03
Representation of N2, %	49.2 ± 1.8	45.3 ± 5.6	0.53
Representation of delta sleep, %	20.7 ± 1.8	26.1 ± 2.7	0.04
Representation of REM, %	19.2 ± 1.8	17.9 ± 1.5	0.43
Representation of slow-wave sleep, %	71.5 ± 1.6	71.7 ± 3.2	0.85
The number of wakefulness segments, min	14.4 ± 2.6	13.0 ± 4.0	0.51
The number of segments N1	2.6 ± 0.5	3.7 ± 2.3	0.64
The number of segments N2	29.7 ± 2.8	23.3 ± 5.8	0.73
The number of delta-sleep segments, min	15.1 ± 1.4	32.7 ± 2.5	0.02
The number of REM segments, min	10.6 ± 2.4	10.7 ± 4.7	0.82
The number of slow sleep segments	47.9 ± 4.1	59.7 ± 12.6	0.55
The average duration of waking segments, min	2.2 ± 0.2	2.8 ± 0.2	0.51
The average duration of segments N1, min	3.3 ± 0.7	1.6 ± 0.1	0.05
The average duration of segments N2, min	8.2 ± 0.9	6.8 ± 1.0	0.48
The average duration of delta-sleep segments, min	17.3 ± 2.6	21.5 ± 1.7	0.18
The average duration of REM segments, min	10.3 ± 1.6	7.6 ± 2.7	0.61
The average duration of slow-wave sleep, min segments, min	28.8 ± 2.5	27.9 ± 1.7	0.93
Total sleep duration, min	431.4 ± 18.6	448.2 ± 38.8	0.71
Sleep time duration, min	12.7 ± 3.4	13.3 ± 7.7	0.66
The number of segments during sleep	58.0 ± 4.4	70.4 ± 8.4	0.23
Number of short awakenings	13.3 ± 2.6	12.0 ± 4.0	0.91
Number of awakenings > 3 min	2.7 ± 0.4	3.0 ± 1.5	0.81
Sleep efficiency index, %	88.1 ± 2.3	90.4 ± 3.7	0.73
The number of completed sleep cycles	4.3 ± 0.1	4.5 ± 0.6	0.89
Average heart rate, beats / min	60.0 ± 1.7	60.0 ± 5.3	0.93
Minimum heart rate, beats / min	36.3 ± 3.5	33.7 ± 5.5	0.82
Maximal heart rate, beats / min.	140.9 ± 9.1	140.0 ± 10.0	1.00
Heart rate variability, beats / min.	104.4 ± 9.7	106.3 ± 6.6	0.72

Note: P — significant changes are calculated between indicators before and after treatment; N1 — the first stage of slow-wave sleep; N2 — the second stage of slow-wave sleep; REM — fast sleep phase

vealed a significant reduction in the severity of most nocturnal symptoms, and the scale of sleep deprivation, fatigue on waking after a night's sleep, a significant ($p < 0.05$) reduction in scores took place. Such symptoms as shallow sleep with many dreams and grinding teeth in sleep remained almost without dynamics.

An analysis of the objective assessment of night sleep according to polysomnography in patients with long-term consequences of mine-explosive injury before and after treatment has been done. The data of polysomnography are given in Table 8.

As can be seen from Table 8, after a course of sensory deprivation positive dynamics of almost all night sleep indicators was determined in the patients under examination. Besides, statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease in the duration and percentage of drowsiness took place. This occurred mainly due to a decrease in the duration of drowsiness episodes.

The duration and percentage of delta-sleep increase was also statistically significant, the latter was provided by an increased number of episodes of delta-sleep during the night.

Thus, under the influence of programmed sensory deprivation sessions

of clinical and neurological symptoms.

The subjective assessment of night sleep according to the questionnaires in the dynamics of the treatment are shown in Table 6.

According to the results of tests after treatment the patients showed positive dynamics, which was manifested by a significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in total indicators to the limit level on the scales of quality of night sleep and Epworth's questionnaire. A detailed analysis of indicators for assessing the quality of night sleep in the dynamics is shown in Table 7.

Repeated testing on the questionnaire to assess the quality of night sleep

there are statistically significant positive changes in the phase of slow-wave sleep, in the form of increasing the content of deep restorative sleep at the background of drowsiness episodes reduction.

Discussion of results

Sleep and wakefulness are inextricably linked functional states, against which human life takes place. Therefore, the causes of pathological conditions observed during wakefulness are preserved during sleep. Accordingly, the presence of clinical symptoms during wakefulness and the possible partial or complete disappearance of symptoms during sleep indicate that it is not the cause of the disease that changes, but the conditions of its manifestation. The essence of this approach is the understanding of the functional state of the brain: wakefulness and sleep are not opposed to each other, but are considered interconnected, in a single cycle [8, 11].

Normally, the night sleep cycle is a period of one and a half hours, during which the sleeper successively goes through 4 stages, starting from drowsiness (stage 1) and ending with the deepest — “delta sleep” (stages 3 and 4), which are the phase of slow sleep. Later they change dramatically in the phase of rapid sleep. After the fast sleep phase, a new sleep cycle begins. During the night a person “passes” through 4 — 6 cycles of sleep. Sleep cycles are different in their structure: in the first half of the night deep delta — sleep dominates, and in the morning — light sleep (stage 2) and REM phase [11, 12].

The function of slow sleep is a restorative one. In this state the restoration of cerebral electrolyte homeostasis disrupted during many hours of pre-awakening takes place. It has been shown that the primary neurons of the visual and auditory cortex cease to respond to modal-specific stimuli and begin to respond more

and more to interoceptive impulses. The latter come to the cortex from internal organs (optimization of internal organ management). This means that without good sleep there can be no good work [1, 11].

Fast sleep is started from a clearly defined center located in the area of the varoli bridge and medulla oblongata. Studies have shown that during sleep, there are outbreaks of high activity of the dopaminergic system. It is believed that this activation is mainly associated with the experience of dreams. All other systems (aminergic) are excluded, their neurons are “silent” throughout the period of fast sleep, and none quantum of norepinephrine, serotonin and histamine in the brain is released [11, 13].

Taking into account the features of the patients under examination, especially in the first three days of hospital stay, they took the sleeping pill “Levana IC”, which improved the process of falling asleep. Subsequently sensory deprivation (SD) was performed. During SD in a specialized chamber, the patient’s body is completely removed from the hydrostatic effect of his blood, the blood supply to the legs is reduced by 15 %, and the blood supply to the brain is increased by 20 %. The load on the musculoskeletal system decreases, which in turn reduces the flow of afferent impulses and the need for increased impulses of energy control centers, reducing the total proprioceptive impulse from the musculoskeletal system to restore the activity of individual muscle segments in organism [10, 14, 15, 17].

Under the conditions of SD we observed the restoration of the balance of the sympathetic and parasympathetic divisions of the autonomic nervous system. As the patient is in a state of psycho-emotional relaxation, it can be assumed that reducing peripheral impulses in the limbic system reduces the synthesis of hormones and stress mediators (adrenaline,

cortisol, norepinephrine, adrenocorticotropic hormone) and increases the formation of endorphins, i.e. deprivation contributes to the departure of consciousness from illness and stress [16]. In our opinion, the more definite effect of the previous appointment of Levana IC is due to the fact that its calming effect reduces the need for tension of humoral regulation, and this contributes to the positive impact of sensory deprivation on the ANS.

Being in SD chamber, as the flow of sensory deprivation decreases, its mind and body, as a single system, are “immersed” in a state in which it is able to perceive itself as a system that acts only in its own interests. Reducing SD reduces the body’s need for adaptation to the environment, and then the system “can direct all its energy to self-renewal,” which significantly improves the body’s condition.

Conclusions

1. Sessions of sensory deprivation in patients with long-term consequences of mild combat brain injury improves functional state of the CNS, which is manifested by positive changes in clinical, electroencephalographic and polysomnographic parameters.
2. According to the visual analysis of EEG it is proved that under the influence of sensory deprivation there is a decrease of cerebral and paroxysmal manifestations of bioelectrical activity of the brain.
3. According to the spectral-coherent analysis of EEG it is determined that under the influence of sensory deprivation there is an increase in inter-central and intrahemispheric interactions of biopotentials in the range of beta LF and HF frequencies in the fronto-central departments. In parieto-occipital parts of brain these indexes decrease which indicates the restruc-

turing of functional integration of brain mechanisms with the restoration of the activity of the frontal lobes of the brain, which control and regulate voluntary mental activity.

4. Sessions of sensory deprivation, according to subjective assessment, help to normalize the quality of night sleep and reduce the severity of daytime sleepiness.
5. According to polysomnography under the influence of sensory deprivation there are positive changes in the internal organization of night sleep, as well as statistically proven improvement in slow-wave sleep, which is manifested by increased deep restorative sleep and drowsiness in the overall sleep structure.
6. Before the onset of sensory deprivation in patients there is a decrease in the autonomic neurotransmitter of the sympathoadrenal system and melatonin, which returned to normal after treatment.

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- Впервые поступила в редакцию 29.06.2022 г.
Рекомендована к печати на заседании редакционной коллегии после рецензирования*